

The genus *Gibberula* (Gastropoda, Cystiscidae) in the Cape Verde Islands with the description of a new species

El género *Gibberula* (Gastropoda, Cystiscidae) en el archipiélago de Cabo Verde con la descripción de una nueva especie

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ABSTRACT

The species of the genus *Gibberula* from the Cape Verde islands are reviewed. There are at least four species, three previously described: *Gibberula lucia* Jousseaume, 1877, *G. rauli* Fernandes, 1987 and *G. rolani* Cossignani and Cecalupo, 2005, and one new species, *G. elvirae* n. sp. is here described. *Gibberula rachmaninovi* Kellner, 2003, is considered here as a synonym of *Volvarina sauliae* (Sowerby, 1846).

RESUMEN

Se revisan las especies del género *Gibberula* del archipiélago de Cabo Verde. Existen, al menos, cuatro especies, tres descritas previamente: *Gibberula lucia* Jousseaume, 1877, *G. rauli* Fernandes, 1987 y *G. rolani* Cossignani y Cecalupo, 2005, y una especie nueva que se describe en este trabajo: *G. elvirae* n. sp. Por último, *Gibberula rachmaninovi* Kellner, 2003, es considerado un sinónimo de *Volvarina sauliae* (Sowerby, 1846).

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Gibberula* belongs to the family Cystiscidae which, together with the closely related family Marginellidae, are known as "Marginelliform" gastropods, and are one of the most conspicuous elements of the West African malacofauna.

The molluscan fauna of the Cape Verde Islands has been studied by many authors: JOUSSEAUME (1877), ROCHEBRUNE (1881a, b), DAUTZENBERG (1910), MELVILL AND STANDEN (1913), BURNAY AND MONTEIRO (1977), SAUNDERS (1977), GARCÍA-TALAVERA AND BACALLADO (1979), COSEL (1982a, b, c), FERNANDES (1987), MORENO AND BURNAY (1999), GUERREIRO AND REINER (2000), KELLNER (2003), ROLÁN (2005) and COSSIGNANI AND CECALUPO (2005).

There are six species names for *Gibberula* listed in the literature, either described with a type locality in the Cape Verde Islands or cited for the Archipelago. The Mediterranean species *Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *G. philippii* (Monterosato, 1878) were erroneously cited in the Cape Verde Islands and are not present in the archipelago. Another species, *Gibberula rachmaninovi* Kellner, 2003, described from the Cape Verde islands as a *Gibberula* will here be shown to belong to a different genus, *Volvarina*. The genus *Gibberula* is represented in the Cape Verde Archipelago by four species, either endemic, as *G. rauli* Fernandes, 1987, *G. rolani* Cossignani and Cecalupo, 2005,

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Table I. Localities studied in the Cape Verde Archipelago with species of the genus *Gibberula*, showing the coordinates and the origin of the samples (see abbreviations used).

Tabla I. Localidades de estudio en el archipiélago de Cabo Verde con especies del género *Gibberula*, mostrando las coordenadas y origen de las muestras (ver abreviaturas utilizadas).

Nº	Island	Locality	Coordinates (Datum WGS84)	Origin of the samples
1	Sal	Ponta Preta	16°48'N; 22°59'W	ER
2	Sal	Rigona	16°47'N; 22°59'W	PEICV and ER
3	Sal	Baia Palmeira	16°45'N; 22°58'W	PEICV
4	Sal	Rabo de Junco	16°41'N; 22°57'W	ER
5	Sal	Baia Mordeira	16°40'N; 22°56'W	ER
6	Sal	Baia Algodoeiro	16°37'N; 22°55'W	ER
7	Sal	Santa Maria	16°35'N; 22°54'W	PEICV
8	Sal	Fiura	16°50'N; 22°54'W	PEICV
9	Sal	Palhona	16°50'N; 22°57'W	ER
10	Sal	Monte Leste	16°49'N; 22°58'W	ER
11	São Vicente	Salamanza	16°54'N; 24°57'W	PEICV
12	São Vicente	Callhau	16°51'N; 24°52'W	RVC-MNHN
13	Boavista	Baia Sal Rei	16°10'N; 22°55'W	PEICV
14	Boavista	Derrubado	16°14'N; 22°46'W	ER
15	Santiago	Praia	14°54'N; 23°30'W	AO
16	Brava	Baia Pedrinha	14°54'N; 24°41'W	ER
17	Brava	Furna	14°53'N; 24°40'W	ER

and the new species described in the present paper, or with a very restricted distribution area, as *G. lucia* Jousseau, 1877, cited also in Senegal (KNUDSEN, 1956; PIN AND BOYER, 1995).

The pigmentation patterns of the head-foot and mantle in the living animals are usually bright and have been shown to be stable and extremely informative for the separation of closely related species (FERNANDES, 1987; GOFAS, 1989a, 1989b, 1990; MORENO AND BURNAY, 1999) and will be given particular attention in this paper. Also the radula features are important for separating species (MORENO AND BURNAY, 1999).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Most of the material examined was collected during the "Primera Expedición Ibérica a Cabo Verde" (PEICV) excursion to the Cape Verde Islands, in which the author took part (August 1985). Specimens were hand-picked while scuba-diving or snorkeling

between 0 and 5 m depth in the islands of Sal, Boavista and São Vicente. Most specimens were collected between -1 and -2 meters on rocky bottoms with coral slabs. Other islands were visited (Santa Luzia, São Nicolau and Santiago) but only a limited sampling effort could be carried out (snorkeling) and no specimens of this genus were obtained.

Other material studied was collected by L.P. Burnay in the years 1975-1976 (IIT), by R. von Cosel in 1978 (São Vicente Island, at MNHN), by E. Rolán in the years 1978, 1979, 1980, 1981, 1986, 1987, 1988 and 2001 (Sal, Boavista and Brava), and by A.D. De Oliveira in 2005 (Santiago). Specimens of *Gibberula oryza* (Lamarck, 1822), the type species of the genus, were studied and photographed alive at Punta Carnero, Cádiz, in the Strait of Gibraltar (1997). All localities studied are shown in Table I and in the map of Figure 1.

The clarification of the complex taxonomic problems in the genus is mainly based on the observation of pigmentation patterns, and therefore required collecting and sorting the animals alive. The

Figure 1. Map of Cape Verde Archipelago and localities where the studied material of the genus *Gibberula* was collected (origin of the samples in brackets). Coordinates in Table I. Sal Island, 1: Ponta Preta (ER); 2: Rigona (PEICV) and (ER); 3: Baía Palmeira (PEICV); 4: Rabo de Junco (ER); 5: Baía Mordeira (ER); 6: Baía Algodoeiro (ER); 7: Santa Maria (PEICV); 8: Fiura (PEICV); 9: Palhona (ER); 10: Monte Leste (ER). São Vicente Island, 11: Salamanca (PEICV); 12: Calhau (RVC-MNHN). Boavista Island, 13: Baía Sal Rei (PEICV); 14: Derrubado (ER). Santiago Island, 15: Praia (AO). Brava Island, 16: Baía Pedrinha (ER); 17: Furna (ER).

Figura 1. Mapa del archipiélago de Cabo Verde y localidades donde se recolectó el material estudiado del género Gibberula (origen de las muestras entre paréntesis). Coordenadas en la Tabla I. Isla de Sal, 1: Ponta Preta (ER); 2: Rigona (PEICV) y (ER); 3: Baía Palmeira (PEICV); 4: Rabo de Junco (ER); 5: Baía Mordeira (ER); 6: Baía Algodoeiro (ER); 7: Santa Maria (PEICV); 8: Fiura (PEICV); 9: Palhona (ER); 10: Monte Leste (ER). Isla de São Vicente, 11: Salamanca (PEICV); 12: Calhau (RVC-MNHN). Isla de Boavista, 13: Baía Sal Rei (PEICV); 14: Derrubado (ER). Isla Santiago, 15: Praia (AO). Isla Brava, 16: Baía Pedrinha (ER); 17: Furna (ER).

living animals were observed under a stereomicroscope, and coloured drawings prepared to take note of the patterns and tones of pigmentation. In some cases, colour slides were also taken.

The radulae were extracted from adult specimens using potassium hydroxide on whole animals soaked in water. At least one radula of each species was observed through a scanning electron microscope (MNCN).

Abbreviations used

AO: Alvaro David De Oliveira Ramos and his private collection (Gulpilhares, Portugal)

ER: Emilio Rolán and his private collection (Vigo, Spain).

IIT: Instituto de Investigação Tropical (Centro de Zoologia), Lisboa, Portugal.

MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid.

MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Laboratoire de Malacologie, Paris, France.

PEICV: Primera Expedición Ibérica al Archipiélago de Cabo Verde (1985).

RVC: Rudo Von Cosel (MNHN, Paris, France).

UAM: Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain (Departamento de Biología, Zoología).

SYSTEMATIC PART

Family CYSTISCIDAE Stimpson, 1865

Genus *Gibberula* Swainson, 1840

Type species *Gibberula zonata* Swainson, 1840 by monotypy (= *Volvaria oryza* Lamarck, 1822), as stated Gofas (1990: 115) (Fig. 17).

The shell of the species of the genus *Gibberula* is ovate-cylindrical, sometimes somewhat pyriform with a very developed body whorl covering almost all of the earlier whorls. The shell is translucent in the smaller species, so that the inner mantle may be visible by transparency. The protoconch is paucispiral as in all marginelliform gastropods. The aperture is elongate and narrow and has anteriorly a rounded siphonal canal. The columella has plaits on its anterior half, decreasing in size towards the apical end. The outer lip, in adults, is always thickened, with usually numerous denticles on the inner margin. The shell surface is glossy, without colour, with spiral pigmented bands or more rarely with wavy axial flames.

The animal (type 4 following COOVERT AND COOVERT, 1995) is active, fast-moving, and creeps on the foot which is truncated anteriorly and rounded posteriorly. The head is small, deeply cleft in two parts and provided

with a pair of short tentacles. The eyes are small, without lateral bulges as in the Marginellidae. The siphon lies over the head and it is cleft on its lower side. The mantle does not cover the shell as other marginelliform gastropods. The pigmented areas are on the upper part of the foot, the head, the siphon and tentacles, and the mantle. The most common colours are black, orange and opaque white. The upper part of the foot, siphon and head are usually more brightly pigmented. When the animal is withdrawn, the pigmentation of the inner mantle may be seen through the shell.

The radula (type 3 following COOVERT AND COOVERT, 1995), is rachiglossan, reduced to a central rachidian tooth per line, which is V-shaped, between 0.008 and 0.042 mm wide, with several cusps (5-11). The ratio shell length/tooth width (L/Wr) in the genus is between 118 and 309 (COOVERT AND COOVERT, 1995).

Gibberula lucia Jousseau, 1877 (Figs. 2-4)

Gibberula lucia Jousseau, 1877: 269-270, pl. V, figs. 11-13 (Santa Luzia Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

Other references:

Marginella (*Glabella*) *lucia* (Jousseau, 1876) [sic]: Tryon, 1883.

Gibberula lucia Jousseau, 1877: Tomlin, 1917; p. 277.

Marginella lucia (Jousseau, 1876) [sic]: Knudsen, 1956; p. 88, Pl. 1, Fig. 4 (Gorée, Senegal).

Marginella lucia (Jousseau, 1876) [sic]: Wagner and Abbott, 1967; p. 156.

Gibberula lucia Jousseau, 1876 [sic]: Pin and Boyer, 1995; p. 56, Figs. 7-9 (Dakar, Senegal).

Other references (doubtful):

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Rochebrune, 1881b; p. 293 (Porto-Praya in Santiago Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Persicula miliaria* (Monterosato) [sic]: García-Talavera and Bacallado, 1979; p. 207 (Mindelo and Gatas in São Vicente Island and Praia in Santiago Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

Type material: 3 syntypes (MNHN) all of 3.5 mm length (Fig. 3 in the present paper).

Other material studied: Santiago Island: Praia, 1 sp., broken (AO) (Fig. 4).

Figures 2-4. *Gibberula lucia*. 2: figures 11, 12 and 13 of the original description by Jousseume (1877); 3: three syntypes of *G. lucia* from Santa Luzia Island (MNHN) (3.5 mm); 4: specimen from Praia, Santiago Island collected by A. Oliveira (23-VII-2005) (4.0 mm).

Figuras 2-4. Gibberula lucia. 2: figuras 11, 12 y 13 de la descripción original de Jousseume (1877); 3: tres sintipos de G. lucia de la isla de Santa Luzia (MNHN) (3,5 mm); 4: ejemplar de Praia, isla de Santiago, recogido por A. Oliveira (23-VII-2005) (4,0 mm).

Remarks: The shell descriptions of JOUSSEAUME (1877) and KNUDSEN (1956) are good. The figure of this species by JOUSSEAUME (1877), reproduced here in Fig. 2, is deficient, but that of KNUDSEN (1956) from Senegal is better. PIN AND BOYER (1995) also made a description of shells from Dakar (Senegal) showing photographs of several specimens. There are no data about the animal and its colour pattern or radula.

Distribution: With the scarce data available, the species lives in Santa Luzia Island (Cape Verde Archipelago), and in the area of Dakar (Senegal), including Gorée Island, where it seems to be more abundant. So, this is the sole

species of the genus living in the Cape Verde Islands that is not considered endemic. It still has a very restricted area of distribution, because Dakar is the closest point of the African continent to the Cape Verde Islands.

Discussion: The species, described with material from the desertic island of Santa Luzia by JOUSSEAUME (1877), has a shell with a very distinct colour pattern of brown lines in four groups: two of them comma-shaped that converge in the central part of the body whorl, another group near the suture and the last one along the base of the shell. This colour pattern matches that of the specimens from Gorée, Dakar (Senegal)

studied by KNUDSEN (1956). There has been no more material of this species recorded from the Cape Verde Islands since the description by JOUSSEAUME (1877), in spite of the numerous malacological expeditions to this area made in the last decades of the XX Century. The species was not cited by several authors who studied the malacofauna of the Cape Verde Islands, including COSEL (1982b) in a work about the molluscan fauna of Santa Luzia, the type locality of this species. Nevertheless a single specimen (Fig. 5) collected by A. Oliveira at

Praia (Santiago Island) (23-VII-2005), confirms the presence of the species in the Cape Verde Islands, and silences the possible doubts that could exist about the Jousseume material.

ROLÁN (2005) reports the name *Gibberula lucia* Jousseume, 1876 [sic] erroneously as a synonym of *Gibberula* sp. 2., but not as a valid species. The species cited as *Gibberula* sp. 2 by ROLÁN (2005) was described in the same year as *Gibberula rolani* by COSSIGNANI AND CECALUPO (2005), and it is hereafter treated as a valid species, different from *G. lucia*.

Gibberula rauli Fernandes, 1987 (Figs. 5, 6, 14)

Gibberula rauli Fernandes, 1987: 265, figs. 3 and c (Sal, Boavista, Maio, Santiago and São Vicente islands, all in the Cape Verde Archipelago).

Gibberula philippii (Monterosato, 1878) [misidentification]: García-Talavera and Bacallado, 1979; p. 207 (Mindelo in São Vicente Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

Gibberula rauli Fernandes, 1987: Rolán, 2005; p. 147, Figs. 642 and 778 (from throughout the Cape Verde Archipelago).

Material studied (all from the Cape Verde Islands): Boavista Island: Derrubado, 2 sp. (ER). Sal Island: Rabo de Junco, 2 sp. (ER). Rigona, 2 sp. (ER). Algodoeiro, 2 sp. (ER). São Vicente Island: Salamanca, 75 sp. + 10 sp. (PEICV). Brava Island: Baía Pedrinha, 137 sp. (ER). Furna, 5 sp. (ER).

Remarks: The shell description by FERNANDES (1987) is correct. This author included drawings of the shell and of the living animal. The shell, which is very transparent, is here shown photographed (Fig. 5). The animal is active and fast. The foot, rounded in its rear end, is longer than the shell when the animal is moving

on the substratum. The head is small, divided into two parts, and the tentacles are very short. The pigmentation pattern (Fig. 14) on the foot and on the inner mantle observed by transparency, is white, with extensive black areas, very irregular in shape in the mantle. The siphon is white.

(Right page) Figures 5-13. Shells and radulae of species of *Gibberula* from Cape Verde Islands. 5, 6. *Gibberula rauli*, Salamanca, São Vicente (PEICV). 5: shells (2.2 and 2.1 mm); 6: radula. 7-11. *Gibberula rolani*. 7: shell from Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV) (5.1 mm); 8: shell from Rigona, Sal (PEICV) (5.0 mm); 9: radula from Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV); 10, 11: teratological double radula from Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV); 10: double radula showing the odontophoral cartilage hoods typical of a cistiscid radula; 11: teeth details of double radula. 12, 13. Holotype of *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp. from Salamanca, São Vicente (PEICV). 12: shell (4.8 x 3.0 mm); 13: radula.

(Página derecha) Figuras 5-13. Conchas y rádulas de especies de *Gibberula* de las islas de Cabo Verde. 5, 6. *Gibberula rauli*, Salamanca, São Vicente (PEICV). 5: conchas (2,2 y 2,1 mm); 6: rádula. 7-11. *Gibberula rolani*. 7: concha de Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV) (5,1 mm); 8: concha de Rigona, Sal (PEICV) (5,0 mm); 9: rádula de Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV); 10, 11: rádula teratológica doble de Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV); 10: rádula doble mostrando la forma de capucha del cartilago odontoforal, típica de una rádula de cistiscido; 11: detalle de los dientes de la rádula doble. 12, 13. Holotipo de *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp. de Salamanca, São Vicente (PEICV). 12: concha (4,8 x 3,0 mm); 13: rádula.

The radula is described and figured here for the first time (Fig. 6). Radular teeth have an arched form with a central cusp prominent but narrower than some lateral cusps. On each side of the central cusp there is a small one, followed by three lateral cusps, the first one large and strong, and then two external ones, smaller. There are 9 cusps in total. The teeth are 0.017 mm width. As the shell length of the specimen dissected for radular study is 2.0 mm, the "shell length/tooth width" ratio (L/Wr) is 118.

Habitat: This species lives in the upper zone of the sublittoral, between 1

and 5 meters depth, on rocky bottoms with sand and algae.

Distribution: An endemic species from the Cape Verde Islands. ROLÁN (2005) stated that *G. rauli* is known from the entire archipelago. The islands reported in the bibliography are: Sal (type locality at Rabo de Junco Beach), Boavista, Maio, Santiago and São Vicente. In the present work it is cited also from Brava Island. *Gibberula philippii* is a Mediterranean species (GOFAS, 1990) erroneously cited from the Cape Verde Islands by GARCÍA-TALAVERA AND BACALLADO (1979).

Gibberula rolani Cossignani and Cecalupo, 2005 (Figs. 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 15)

Gibberula sp. 1: Rolán, 2005; p. 148, only part (Figs. 643-644) (endemic from the Cape Verde Islands).

Gibberula sp. 2: Rolán, 2005; p. 148, (Fig. 645) (endemic from the Cape Verde Islands).

Gibberula rolani Cossignani and Cecalupo, 2005: p. 6-7, 6 Figs. (Mordeira in Sal Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

Other references (doubtful: could also be *G. elvirae* or *G. lucia*):

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Rochebrune, 1881b; p. 293 (Porto-Praya in Santiago Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Gibberula oryza* Lamarck, 1822: Dautzenberg, 1910; p. 43-44 (Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Melvill and Standen, 1913: p. 342 (São Vicente, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Persicula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Saunders, 1977; p. 14 (Matiota in São Vicente and Palmeira in Sal Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Persicula miliaria* (Monterosato) [sic]: García-Talavera and Bacallado, 1979; p. 207 (Mindelo and Gatas in São Vicente Island and Praia in Santiago Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Cosel, 1982a; p. 20 (São Vicente, Sal and Santiago Islands, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Cosel, 1982c; p. 57 (Cape Verde Archipelago).

Material studied (all from Cape Verde Islands): Boavista Island: Sal Rei, 6 sp. + 1 juv. + 1 juv. + 1 juv. (UAM). Derrubado, 2 sp. + 1 juv. (ER). Sal Island: without locality, 6 sp. + 1 sp. + 1 sp. (IIT). Palmeira, 1 sp. + 1 sp. + 2 sp. (UAM). Ponta Preta, 10 sp. + 9 juv. (ER). Palhona, 6 sp. + 4 sp. + 4 sp. + 4 juv. (ER). Rabo de Junco, 27 sp. + 10 juv. (ER). Mordeira, 5 sp. + 1 sp. (ER). Monte Leste, 8 sp. + 3 sp. (ER). Santa María, 1 sp. (UAM). Rigona, 1 sp. + 1 sp. (UAM), 6 sp. + 1 juv. (ER). Algodoeiro, 4 sp. (ER). Fiura, 1 sp. (UAM). ?Brava Island: Baía Pedrinha, 1 sp. (ER).

Description: The species description by COSSIGNANI AND CECALUPO (2005) is basically correct, but based only on the shell. This is pyriform, narrow in the anterior end with a broad and rounded body whorl. There are 5-6 plaits in the columella, decreasing in size posteriorly, and 14-18 small denticles on the inner side of the outer lip. In general the shell

has a dark brown sutural band, not always present. Several specimens are plain white (Fig. 7) or a pale yellow, and other shells have two or three spirals bands of a very pale brown (Fig. 8). Some specimens have one broad spiral and brown band in the central part of the body whorl, a result of the fusion of both anterior pigmented lines.

The animal, described here for the first time (Fig. 15, from Boavista Island material) is active and slithers fast on the substratum with the foot, which is larger than the shell when totally extended. The foot is ovate in the metapodium and truncated in the propodium, translucent-white with peripheral orange lines and patches, and a conspicuous central line on the posterior end (Fig. 15). Some specimens do not have the metapodium pigmented, but have orange lines in the propodium. The head is small with a central split. There is one orange line on each side of the head from the inner part of the eyes to the anterior end of the snout. The tentacles are short, with a small and central band, also orange. The siphon is small, of a pale yellow colour. The inner mantle, that can be observed by transparency, is also very variable, dark with white lobes, orange with white patches, or clear with dark or orange dots.

The radula is described and figured here for the first time (Fig. 9, from Boavista Island material). Radular teeth were studied from two specimens. The teeth have an arched form with a prominent central cusp. There are on each side of the central cusp a small one (not always present) and 4 (3 or 5 in some cases) strong lateral cusps (there are 9-10 cusps in total). The same pattern of cusps are observed every three teeth, so that two adjacent teeth never have the same cusps, and the lateral cusps of similar length do not match in the same position. A teratological specimen was observed with two complete radulae in the same bucal bulb (Figs. 10-11), one of them placed over the other. The teeth of both radulae are similar to that previously described for a normal specimen. The average tooth width is 0.026 mm. As the average shell length of the specimens is 5.0 mm, the "shell length/tooth width" ratio (L/Wr) for this species is 192.

Habitat: This species lives in the upper sublittoral area, between 1 and 5 m depth, where it was observed under stones on rocky bottoms with sand.

Distribution: *G. rolani* is an endemic species of the Cape Verde Islands. We have found this species only on Sal and Boavista islands, where it is frequent. We studied also a single specimen from Brava Island that probably belongs to this species, with a similar form and 2 spiral bands of pale brown, one central and another on the base. Some of the references of *Gibberula miliaria* from the Cape Verde Islands (considered here as corresponding to *G. rolani*) cited other islands in its distribution, such as Santiago (ROCHEBRUNE, 1881b; COSEL, 1982a) and São Vicente (SAUNDERS, 1977; GARCÍA-TALAVERA AND BACALLADO, 1979; COSEL, 1982a). If *G. rolani* really lives on Santiago and São Vicente, a fact that should be confirmed with new material, the species would achieve a distribution throughout all the island groups of the archipelago.

Discussion: The description of this species by COSSIGNANI AND CECALUPO (2005) was made immediately (November 2005) after the publication in April of the same year of the book by ROLÁN (2005) on the malacological fauna of the Cape Verde Archipelago. ROLÁN (2005) included two *Gibberula* species without specific names (sp. 1 and sp. 2, on page 148), stating that they were in course of description. The hasty description of *Gibberula rolani* by COSSIGNANI AND CECALUPO (2005) disregards the ethical recommendation of the International code of Zoological Nomenclature because they knew the situation regarding the case and stated that their new species was present in the book by ROLÁN (2005) as "*Gibberula* sp. 1 (Figs. 643-644, 776) and *Gibberula* sp. 2 (Fig. 645) pag. 148".

It is most probably this species which has been misidentified as *Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) by several authors, but *G. miliaria* lives only in the Mediterranean Sea (GOFAS, 1990). There are obvious differences in the pigmentation pattern between both species, particularly on the foot, where *G. rolani* has a clearly defined pattern with peripheral orange lines and patches. Also, the head of *G. rolani* has single

Figures 14-16. Live animals of *Gibberula* species from Cape Verde Islands. 14: *Gibberula rauli*, Salamanza, São Vicente (PEICV) (2.2 mm); 15: *Gibberula rolani*, Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV) (5.0 mm); 16: holotype of *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp., Salamanza, São Vicente (PEICV) (4.8 mm).

Figuras 14-16. Animales vivos de especies de Gibberula de las islas de Cabo Verde. 14: Gibberula rauli, Salamanza, São Vicente (PEICV) (2,2 mm); 15: Gibberula rolani, Sal Rei, Boavista (PEICV) (5,0 mm); 16: holotipo de Gibberula elvirae n. sp. Salamanza, São Vicente (PEICV) (4,8 mm).

orange lines and a small band in the tentacles, whereas in *G. miliaria* the foot and head patterns are more elaborate, with different colours and small dots (COOVERT, 1987; GOFAS, 1990). The radula of *G. miliaria* was studied by Bandel (1984, Fig. 297: as *Persicula miliaria*, from Banyuls-sur-Mer, France, Mediterranean Sea) and reproduced by COOVERT (1989, Fig. 19). The teeth of *G. rolani* are similar to those of *G. miliaria*, but in the former the lateral cusps are stronger than in the latter species. Also, the teeth of *G. rolani* have 8-9 cusps against 9-11 in *G. miliaria*.

About the teratological radulae studied (Figs. 10-11) it seems that in this strange specimen there are two radular sacs, instead of one, but only a pair of odontophoral cartilage hoods (Fig. 10), characteristic of the "cysticid radula", so

called by COOVERT AND COOVERT (1995). There is no information of a similar case known in the marginelliform gastropods (COOVERT AND COOVERT, 1995).

DAUTZENBERG (1910) included the Cape Verde Islands in the distribution of the species *Gibberula oryza*, but this species lives only on the continental African coasts from Senegal to the Strait of Gibraltar (GOFAS, 1990). Some shell patterns of *G. rolani*, like those with a broad band remind of the neotype of *G. oryza* figured by GOFAS (1990, Fig. 2), or shells without bands, which look like specimens of *G. oryza* from Ceuta (Fig. 3 in GOFAS, 1990). However, the shell of *G. rolani* is smaller (up to 5 mm length) than that of *G. oryza* (up to 8 mm length). The colour pattern of the animal is also different between these two species; *G. rolani* has only orange lines and patches,

Figures 17-18. Live animals of *Gibberula* species. 17: *Gibberula oryza*, Punta Carnero, Cádiz, Spain (7 mm); 18: holotype of *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp., Salamanca, São Vicente (PEICV) (4.8 mm).

Figuras 17-18. Animales vivos de especies de Gibberula. 17: Gibberula oryza, Punta Carnero, Cádiz, España (7 mm); 18: holotipo de Gibberula elvirae n. sp. Salamanca, São Vicente (PEICV) (4,8 mm).

restricted in general to the pedal margin of the foot, while in *G. oryza* the pigmentation pattern is outspread, with orange, yellow and violet small dots over all the foot (GOFAS, 1990: Pl. 1, Figs. a-a'; see also Fig. 17 in the present paper). The radula of *G. oryza* of a specimen from Ceuta was studied by GOFAS (1990, Fig. 1). The arched form of the teeth and the number of cusps are very similar between *G. rolani* and *G. oryza* (9-10 and 11 cusps,

respectively), but in the first species the tooth width is significantly smaller (0.026 mm) than that of the second (0.038 mm). The "shell length/tooth width" ratio (L/Wr) is similar in both species, 192 and 187 respectively, but the length shell of the first species is 5 mm, while in *G. oryza* it is more or less 7 mm (GOFAS, 1990 did not state the shell length of the specimen dissected for obtention of the radula figured).

Gibberula elvirae n. sp. (Figs. 12, 13, 16 and 18)

Gibberula sp. 1: Rolán, 2005; p. 148, only part (Fig. 776) (endemic from Cape Verde Island).

Other references (doubtful):

?*Gibberula oryza* Lamarck, 1822: Dautzenberg, 1910; p. 43-44 (Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Melvill and Standen, 1913: p. 342 (São Vicente, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Persicula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Saunders, 1977; p. 14 (Matiota in São Vicente and Palmeira in Sal Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Persicula miliaria* (Monterosato) [sic]: García-Talavera and Bacallado, 1979; p. 207 (Mindelo and Gatas in São Vicente Island and Praia in Santiago Island, Cape Verde Archipelago).

?*Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758): Cosel, 1982a; p. 20 (São Vicente, Sal and Santiago Islands, Cape Verde Archipelago).

Type material: Holotype, specimen 4.8 × 3.0 mm, from Salamanza, São Vicente (Cape Verde Islands), from a lot of one specimen (UAM no. 229) collected on 20-VIII-1985 by PEICV (deposited in MNCN, no. 15.05/60007); Paratypes 1 and 2 (the latest with the siphonal canal broken) from Baía do Calhau, São Vicente, from a lot of five specimens (two broken) (MNHN, Rudo von Cosel Coll., 21-XII-1978) (both deposited in MNHN).

Other material studied: ?Brava Island: Baía Pedrinha, 3 sp. (ER).

Type locality: Salamanza, São Vicente, 1 m depth.

Etymology: The species is dedicated to my daughter Elvira Moreno Martín 11 years old, for her constant effort, sensitivity and enthusiasm without limits.

Description: The shell is oval-cylindrical, quite elongate, with the body whorl covering almost all the previous spirals. There are 6-7 plaits in the columella, decreasing in size adapically. The outer lip goes from the sutural area to the siphonal canal, is swollen and has 15-16 well defined denticles on the inner side. The surface is smooth and brilliant and somewhat translucent, so that the internal mantle can be seen by transparency. The protoconch is paucispiral like in all marginelliform gastropods, and the adult shell has approximately 2.5 whorls. The aperture is narrow and elongated, and it has in its anterior part a wide siphonal canal. The shell colour seems very constant, with four brown bands, plus one in a subsutural position. These four bands, more or less equidistant, are narrow but well contrasted, except the second one (numbered from de suture) which is broader than the others, and constitutes the central band very characteristic of the species.

The animal is active, with the foot longer than the shell when it is completely extended. The foot is truncated in the anterior part and rounded in its

rear end. The head is small, divided into two parts with a pair of very short tentacles. The eyes are near the base of the tentacles. The siphon, placed on the head, is short and wide. The pigmentation pattern is very typical, with intense colours: white, black and orange (Figs. 16 and 18). The head is black, with two yellow specks in the center and two orange ones on the snout. Behind each eye there is an orange speck, as on the end of every tentacle. The siphon has black spots and the end is bordered with orange. The foot presents lateral and radial black bands, which reach the pedal border, whereas in the anterior and posterior parts they end before reaching the rim. The margin of the foot has a thin orange line, which is continued on the propodium or anterior part, and intermittent on the central part and end of the metapodium. On the propodium and the posterior metapodium numerous orange dots exist. The internal mantle, seen by transparency, is black in colour with large white, irregular, but very definite patches. The only animal observed was the holotype.

The radula has approximately 150 tooth lines (data from the only animal

studied, the holotype). The teeth are 0.036 mm width (Fig. 13). As the shell length of the specimen dissected for radular study is 4.8 mm, the "shell length/tooth width" ratio (L/Wr) is 133. The teeth are arched and have a more prominent central cusp with 4-5 minor denticles on each side (10-11 cusps in total). The central cusp has a broad base and is blunt. The adjacent cusps to the central one (1 or 2 in number) are smaller than the other lateral denticles. Every 3 teeth, approximately, the same pattern of denticulation is observed. There are never two identical contiguous teeth and the lateral cusps of equal size do not coincide with the same line.

Habitat: This species lives in the upper sublittoral area, between 1 and 2 m depth, on a rocky bottom with algae.

Distribution: *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp. is an endemic species of the Cape Verde Islands. We have found this species with certainty only on São Vicente Island, where seems to be limited to the North-East coast. A lot of 3 specimens from the island of Brava (Baia Pedrinha) probably belongs to this species, considering the presence of 4 bands on the shell as described previously. The species has not been found on the eastern islands, such as Sal and Boavista, in spite of the numerous samples obtained from both.

Discussion: *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp. is different from any other species known in this genus, both for the coloration and shape of the shell, and for the pigmentation pattern of the animal, including the other species with similar length shell that live in the Cape Verde Islands: *G. lucia* and *G. rolani*. The central expanded band of the shell recalls certain patterns of *G. oryza*, but the latter does not possess the thin basal bands, next to the siphonal canal and to the suture, respectively. As stated by

GOFAS (1990), when the shells of *G. oryza* have a pattern with spiral pigmentation, they can show either a broad and central band like the neotype, or two broad and parallel bands in a central position (his figures 2 and 4, respectively). However, the shell of *G. elvirae* n. sp. has up to 4 bands, and only the second (from the suture) is broader than the others. The length and general shape of the shell is also different; *G. elvirae* is smaller (less than 5 mm) and of cylindrical shape, while *G. oryza* is larger (up to 8 mm) and piriform.

The animal of *G. elvirae* n. sp. was illustrated by ROLÁN (2005, Fig. 776) as *Gibberula* sp. 2 (actually that specimen is the holotype designated here and that photograph the same image reproduced here in Figure 18). The colour pattern of the animal of *G. elvirae* is different from that of *G. oryza* shown by GOFAS (1990: Pl. 1, Figs. a-a') and in the present paper (Fig. 17), in having: 1) several black patches on the foot, on the head and on the siphon, 2) the orange dots of the propodium arranged forming a well defined line, and 3) the tentacles with a broad orange band.

Like for the previous species, the "V"-shape of the teeth and the number of cusps are very similar between *G. elvirae* n. sp. and *G. oryza* (10-11 and 11 cusps, respectively). Also, the tooth width is similar between both species (0.036 and 0.038 mm, respectively), but in the first species the "shell length/tooth width" ratio (L/Wr) is 133 and in *G. oryza* is 187, because the shell in the last species is larger. GOFAS (1990) did not state the shell length of the dissected specimen used to obtain the figured radula, and here it is assumed to be of 7 mm, an average of the specimens mentioned by the same author from the Strait of Gibraltar.

Other species described from the Cape Verde Islands

Gibberula jousseaumi Rochebrune, 1881, described with type locality in Porto Praia, Santiago Island, was cited later as *Marginella jousseaumi* by BURNAY

AND MONTEIRO (1977), as *Gibberula jousseaumi* by COSEL (1982a), and as *Persicula jousseaumi* by GUERREIRO AND REINER (2000), all of them with material

from Sal Island. However, this name was considered as a subjective synonym of *Volvarina sauliae* (Sowerby, 1846) by MORENO AND BURNAY (1999) in their revision of the genus *Volvarina* in the Cape Verde Islands. *Volvarina sauliae* has a shell that resembles a *Gibberula*, but has a typical radula of the genus *Volvarina*, with rectangular and “comblike” shaped teeth, flat and multicusped (type 6 following COOVER, 1989), while the radula of genus *Gibberula* is of type 3 (according to the same author), with teeth strongly concave in the basal edge, “V”-shaped and relatively few cusps.

The taxon *Gibberula rachmaninovi* Kellner, 2003, was introduced recently in a very poor description based only on a shell from Sal Island, without animal

and radula data. ROLÁN (2005) in his book on the mollusks from the Cape Verde Islands considers as a valid species *Volvarina sauliae* (p. 146, Figs 635-636, from Furna, Brava Island, which is the same specimen shown by MORENO AND BURNAY, 1999, Fig. 37, actually coming from Baia Pedrinha in the same island), and also *Gibberula rachmaninovi* (p. 148, Figs. 1193-1194, holotype from Santa Maria, Sal Island). MORENO AND BURNAY (1999: p. 113 and Fig 35) designated and figured a neotype of *Volvarina sauliae* to stabilize the nomenclature of this species. The holotype of *G. rachmaninovi* matches the neotype of *V. sauliae* in all respects, and therefore the first name is considered here a synonym of *Volvarina sauliae* (Sowerby, 1846).

DISCUSSION

The genus *Gibberula* is represented in the Cape Verde Archipelago by four species, three previously described (*Gibberula lucia* Jousseume, 1877; *Gibberula rauli* Fernandes, 1987; and *Gibberula rolani* Cossignani and Cecalupo, 2005), and the new species described here *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp.

Gibberula jousseaumi Rochebrune, 1881, and *Gibberula rachmaninovi* Kellner, 2003, are considered here synonyms of *Volvarina sauliae* (Sowerby, 1846). The names of the Mediterranean species *Gibberula miliaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *G. philippii* (Monterosato, 1878) are erroneously included in the Cape Verde Islands because these species are not present in the archipelago.

Among the *Gibberula* species that live in Cape Verde Islands, there are two clearly differentiated groups, which are equivalent to those already known from the Mediterranean, where GOFAS (1990) speaks about the “group of *G. oryza*” and the “group of *G. philippii*”, based on shell length, shell transparency, pigmentation patterns of the animal and most frequent colours. In Cape Verde waters, one group is constituted by “large” species (for the dimensions of the genus), of 3.5-5 mm long (as *G. lucia*, *G.*

rolani and *G. elvirae* n. sp.), whereas another group is represented by only one “small” species, of approximately 2 mm long (*G. rauli*). The number of *Gibberula* species (four, in the present paper) present in the Cape Verde Archipelago is smaller than that of *Volvarina* species (nine, in MORENO AND BURNAY, 1999), a genus of the family Marginellidae. It is curious that the opposite happens in the Mediterranean, where there are more species of *Gibberula* (also nine, according to GOFAS, 1990), than of *Volvarina* (only one, according to GOFAS, 1989a). So, in the North Eastern Atlantic Ocean the diversity of *Volvarina* species is highest in warm waters, and specially in the Cape Verde Islands, while the diversity of *Gibberula* species is highest along temperate coasts, principally in the Mediterranean Sea. Also along the Angolan coast, in the southeast Atlantic Ocean, there is a higher diversity of species for the genus *Gibberula*, with at least 11 described species (GOFAS, 1989b).

The radular teeth, their size, shape and number of cusps, are also important to discriminate species in the genus *Gibberula*. Among the studied species the smallest radula is that of *G. rauli*, with

only 0.017 mm tooth width. However, the “shell length/tooth width” ratio (L/Wr) is 118, exactly the lowest values cited for the genus by COOVERT AND COOVERT (1995). This means that the radula is the largest in comparison to the shell among the *Gibberula* species known. On the contrary the radula of *G. rolani*, although larger (average of 0.026 mm tooth width), is proportionally smaller in relation to the animal, with a “shell length/tooth width” ratio (L/Wr) of 192. The largest radula of the studied species is that of *G. elvirae* n. sp. (0.036 mm tooth width), almost the same size as that of *G. oryza*. Nevertheless, the height of the shell of *G. elvirae* n. sp. (up to 5 mm) is clearly smaller than that of *G. oryza* (up to 8 mm), and therefore, the “shell length/tooth width” ratio (L/Wr) in this species is smaller (133) than that of the other species mentioned: *G. rolani* and *G. oryza* (with L/Wr ratio of 192 and 187, respectively).

All species studied here have a restricted distribution area and are endemic to the Cape Verde Islands, except *G. lucia* Jousseaume, 1877, cited also from Dakar, Senegal (KNUDSEN, 1956; PIN AND BOYER, 1995), the closest point of the African continent to the Cape Verde Islands. There are relatively few data about the distribution of the species within the Archipelago, in part due to the difficulty in determining the species in the absence of information on the animal colour pattern and radular data. Also, the majority of previous publications that included *Gibberula* species from Cape Verde Islands cited names of Mediterranean species (*G. miliaria* and *G. philippii*), or from the continental coasts (as *G. oryza*) and therefore these records are difficult to assign to the species now considered valid in the Archipelago.

The species that has a wider distribution is *G. rauli*, that lives on Sal (type locality), Boavista, Maio, São Vicente, Santiago and Brava. According to ROLÁN (1991, on the genus *Conus*), and MORENO AND BURNAY (1999, on the genus *Volvarina*), there are several natural barriers between islands in the Cape

Verde Archipelago. The main barrier divides the Archipelago into two groups, that of the South East (including Sal, Boavista, Maio, Santiago, Fogo and Brava) and that of the North West (including São Nicolau, Santa Luzia, São Vicente and Santo Antão). In the first group there are also important barriers between Sal and Boavista-Maio, and between Santiago-Fogo-Brava and Maio-Boavista. So, *G. rauli* is present in all the groups and subgroups of islands in the Archipelago, and probably lives on all the islands. *Gibberula rolani*, described from Sal is here confirmed from Boavista, where it is common. A single specimen from Brava studied here, considered with some doubts as belonging to this species, might indicate its presence in the southern group of islands. The old material (from publications before 1987) that cited the Mediterranean species *G. miliaria* could correspond to *G. rolani*, with doubts because they might correspond also to other species. These distribution data include also São Vicente of the North group of islands. If the presence of *G. rolani* was confirmed in Brava and São Vicente, the distribution of the species would include all groups and important sub-groups of islands. Nevertheless, for the moment, with confirmed information, its distribution is restricted to Sal and Boavista, the easternmost islands which are closest to the African coast. *Gibberula elvirae* n. sp. is described here only from São Vicente specimens which is the type locality. There is a small lot of 3 specimens from Brava (ER) that have a very pale coloured shell, but with a pattern similar to that of the type material of *G. elvirae* n. sp. For the moment, this new species could be considered as endemic to São Vicente, with reservations, pending verification of the small lot of 3 specimens from Brava or its presence on other islands. Finally, *G. lucia*, the first species described from Cape Verde Islands, is the only one that we can consider to be not endemic, being found also in Senegal. There were no data of this species in the Cape Verde Islands since its description and all along the XIX and XX centuries, whereas on the contrary, there

was good material from Senegal. In the present work a single specimen collected at Santiago (AO), confirms the presence of the species in the Cape Verde Islands, if there was any doubt about the correct origin of the material studied by Jousseume.

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